

THE ART OF ACTING IN MODERN PUPPET THEATER IS UNIQUE FEATURES

Abdullayeva Ozodakhan Muradjonovna.

Student of Theater Art, Puppet Production Technology, 3rd stage.

Scientific supervisor: Juraboyev Bekzodjon

Abstract: Among the performing arts, the most miraculous, the most mysterious and the most joyful art is the art of puppet theater. In this case, every object, every work, every action serves only for the entertainment of children - young viewers. Puppeteers give life to the doll and create a wonderful world in the child's delicate heart like a flower, and in their clear, innocent eyes.

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Among the performing arts, the most miraculous, the most mysterious and the most joyful art is the art of puppet theater. In this case, every object, every work, every action serves only for the entertainment of children - young viewers. Puppeteers give life to the doll and create a wonderful world in the child's delicate heart like a flower, and in their clear, innocent eyes. It is natural that a child who has come to the puppet theater once will be always fond of this place. It takes several months to prepare one performance of puppeteers who create the world of fairy tales before the eyes of children. First, the discussion of the new pesa, then the appearance of the characters of the pesa, stage decorations, decorations, and then the process of the artist making the puppets and giving them their own character. The next step is for the director and actors to work with the puppets.

And finally, when the rehearsals are over and the premiere is shown, the puppeteers begin to observe how the children accept the product of their hard work for several months. With their roles, they take the young audience into the magical world of puppets, seeing, sensing and feeling the children's open communication with the birds, plants, animals and other things they play. stand At the same time, amazing changes are taking place in the mental world of the children who are confident in the mysterious actions on the stage, on the contrary, the various whispers and voices of the children, which are heard from the auditorium, are the most important for the puppeteers. minutes.

The actor of the puppet theater mainly performs in the theater. Dolls help him in this. He uses all kinds of puppets in his work: puppets with gloves, strings, trots, tablets and shadow puppets. The activities of puppet theater actors are different from actors in other fields. It embodies the emotional movements of moving the doll and reveals the content of the work to the viewer.

The content, artistry, and attractiveness of the creative work in this theater are directly reflected in the performance of the actors. The actor is literally the face of the theater.

Actor (lat. actor - performer) - actor, performer of roles in drama, opera, ballet, puppet theater, pop, circus, cinema, radio and television. He creates a lively artistic image with the help of his body, voice, mind, emotions and abilities. The main responsibility falls on the actors themselves. For this reason, over the years, specific features of acting skills have emerged and specific schools of acting art have been formed.

Today and in our modern lifestyle, the national school of acting, especially puppet theater acting, embodies certain characteristics.

"Live performance" is widely popular in modern puppet theaters. He is an actor he plays the puppet while acting himself in front of the audience. In such theaters, any object is chosen as a puppet - from household items to a specially prepared object - the animated character is controlled by an actor.

In general, the art of puppet theater differs from other types of theater art by its characteristic of creating a unique image. A puppeteer gives life to a piece of art created by a theater actor, an artist and a puppeteer, i.e. a puppet. Through the puppet, the actor expresses his heartache, his love for nature, his motherland, his dreams and hopes from behind the curtain, which he could not tell the audience. That's when a miracle happens on the puppet stage. An ordinary object - material comes to life, and the viewer believes that it lives, breathes and exists like a person, and cries, laughs and grieves with the doll.

One of the most important tasks of a puppet theater actor in the learning process is the development of hand plasticity and precise movement. In order to learn body plasticity, a puppet theater actor should also visit museums and exhibitions, observe animals in the zoo, nature a lot and remember what he saw. Actors have to learn the anatomy and movement techniques of the doll. At the same time, it is desirable for them to know the laws of balance, fulcrum, and plastic possibilities. For a puppeteer actor, it is not only this, but it is necessary to observe the movement in transition to a state and reflect it in the puppet. For example, moving from a standing position to a sitting position, from a walking position to a running position, from a sitting position to a lying position.

We come across a lot of opinions and views on the professional characteristics of puppet theater actors. First of all, dedication to one's field. This is a common trait

for all industry professionals. Because a creator who cannot love his field quickly overcomes difficulties, fulfills his tasks at the tip of his hand, does not enjoy his creativity. This is the main obstacle to development in the field.

Working through mental, physical, and mental pressure in puppet theater acting requires a unique skill, constant self-improvement, patience, and experience. Therefore, the puppet theater actor has a double responsibility and complexity compared to other areas of acting. In order to transfer their feelings to an inanimate object, in reality, actors must have a strong psychological outlook and acting position. This opportunity is formed in creators who really love the field.

Any practical process, any type of creativity, cannot achieve a result without theory. In general, a puppet theater actor should first of all have an understanding of the theater's historical origin, stages of development, development factors, main types and trends, and its characteristics. In the second place, the artist should have knowledge and skills regarding the theoretical issues specific to acting skills: technique, approach, method, style, physical rules, rules of skill formation.

An old artist cannot become an actor. Since the current task of the puppet theater is to serve children, the actor must remain a child, think like a child, and understand children. The next important feature is that the actors of the puppet theater are experts in child psychology. In this, the actor should try to learn the children's character, what they want and don't like, and how to influence them.

The creator who "makes the product" knows his "customers", their It is a fact that does not require proof that he should be able to understand his needs in advance. Some dramaturgical situations in plays intended for children make the viewer involuntarily laugh. In delivering these humorous situations, the actor is required to

have extraordinary childlike cheerfulness, gaiety and playfulness.

For example, when reviving the characters of the play "Three Funny Pigs" in the repertoire of the Republican Puppet Theater, the actors should first of all pay special attention to humor and be able to reflect it through puppets. The reason is that the character of the characters is exaggerated by the actor in order to reach and influence the children.

First of all, speech is created on the basis of the text of any artistic work, and its basis is words. The perfection, logicity and artistic level of the dramaturgy are important in this. "Speech not only creates conditions for the formation of thought and its logical direction, but is also a tool that influences the listener and convinces him of certain things. Through speech, the speaker forces the interlocutor to understand his thoughts, accept them as he understands and feels.

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